

NATURAL GLUCOSIDES. PART I. THE CONSTITUTION OF THE GLUCOSIDE PRESENT IN *MURRAYA EXOTICA*.

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From the flowers of *Murraya exotica*, Linn. (N. O. *Rutaceae*) de Vry and Blas (*Z. Chem.*, 1869, 310; van Rijn, "Die Glykoside," 1931, p. 256) isolated a bitter, crystalline glucoside which was called murrayin. According to these investigators it has the molecular formula, $C_{18}H_{22}O_{10}$, $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$, and a melting point of 170° . It was found to dissolve in alkali with a yellow colour and a greenish-blue fluorescence. The hydrolysis of murrayin by dilute sulphuric acid afforded murrayetin according to the equation :

Murrayetin, which formed small rhombic needles, m.p. 110° , dissolved in aqueous alkali with a blue fluorescence and formed a yellow lead salt.

From the air-dried petals of *M. exotica* we have been able to isolate a white crystalline glucoside in an yield of 1.3%. It melts at 218° , has a bitter taste and dissolves in alkali forming a yellow solution, which, unlike murrayin, does not show any greenish-blue fluorescence. This glucoside was found to contain 8.55% methoxy group. Hydrolysis with dilute sulphuric acid gave a crystalline aglucone which melts at 202.4° . It dissolves in alkali with an intense blue fluorescence, but unlike murrayetin does not give a yellow precipitate with lead acetate. The aglucone contained 16.17% methoxy groups. We thought that the aglucone might be identical with scopoletin (II), inasmuch as the analysis, colour reactions and the melting point of our aglucone agreed well with those of scopoletin. To confirm the identity of the two compounds, we methylated our aglucone and obtained a white crystalline methyl derivative, m.p. 142° , which was insoluble in alkali. When mixed with a synthetic specimen of esculetin dimethylether (III), which melted at 141.2° , there was no depression in melting point. It, therefore, follows that the glucoside isolated by us from the flowers of *M. exotica* is nothing but scopolin (I), the m.p. of which is reported to be $215-17^\circ$. We believe that de Vry and Blas had an impure specimen of scopolin in their hands and this they called murrayin.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

Isolation of Scopolin.—Air-dried petals (150 g.) of *M. exotica*, which were collected from the suburbs of Calcutta in June, were refluxed with 17 litres of rectified spirit for two hours and filtered hot. The extraction was repeated thrice with the same volume of alcohol. The combined filtrates were concentrated under reduced pressure to about 400 c.c. and treated, while still hot, with a saturated aqueous solution of lead acetate till there was no further precipitate. The yellow lead salt was filtered off and washed with hot alcohol. The lead salt was suspended in hot alcohol (300 c.c.) and saturated with sulphuretted hydrogen and the lead sulphide filtered off. The orange filtrate on concentration did not give any crystalline residue.

The filtrate, left after the removal of the lead salt, was freed from lead by means of sulphuretted hydrogen and the clear yellow filtrate was distilled under reduced pressure to remove alcohol. The residue was taken up with 100 c.c. of hot water and repeatedly shaken with chloroform (15 c.c. were used each time). During extraction with chloroform, a light brown voluminous precipitate separated out which was collected. The aqueous filtrate gave a further quantity of the precipitate on concentration on the water-bath and cooling. The combined precipitates were thrice crystallised from methyl alcohol (charcoal) when colourless needles, m.p. 218°, were obtained; yield 1.96 g. It is easily soluble in hot water and aqueous alkali, but insoluble in chloroform. (Found in material dried at 110° in *vacuo*: OMe, 8.55. $C_{16}H_{18}O_9$ requires OMe, 8.76 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the Glucoside: Formation of (II).—The glucoside (0.358 g.) dissolved in water (20 c.c.) was heated with 2 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid for 4 hours at 100°. The solution was then extracted eight times with chloroform, 10 c.c. being used each time. The combined extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed on the

water-bath. The brownish crystalline residue was distilled in high vacuum and then crystallised from acetone, when almost colourless needles, m.p. $202-4^{\circ}$, were obtained; yield 0.13 g. (Found: OMe, 16.17. $C_{10}H_8O_4$ requires OMe, 16.15 per cent).

Methylation of (II): Formation of Esculetin Dimethylether.—0.05 G. of (II) was mixed with 0.042 g. of methyl iodide, 5 c.c. of acetone and 0.1 g. of anhydrous potassium carbonate and the mixture was refluxed for 6 hours on the water-bath. It was then filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. The residue was washed with cold water, dried and distilled in high vacuum. The distillate was finally crystallised from methyl alcohol when colourless needles, m.p. 142° , were obtained. Esculetin was methylated in a similar manner using the calculated quantity of methyl iodide and the dimethylether, m.p. $141-2^{\circ}$, did not depress the m. p. of the above compound.

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